

Enzymatic potentials of Lactic Acid Bacteria and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* from Fresh and Soured Palm Wine

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Abstract

The enzymatic potentials of Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* isolated from fresh and soured palm wine samples were determined from 50 palm wine samples collected from Ariam, Umudike and Umunneochi in Abia State. Two LAB: *Lactobacillus plantarium* and *Leuconostic Mesenteroides* and two yeasts: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Saccharomyces uvarum* were isolated from the palm wine samples. The isolates were screened for amylase, cellulase, protease, pectinase and xylanase production using Agar Well Plate Method to determine their ability to produce these enzymes. Among 88mLAB isolated, 20 were able to exhibit amylase production, 15 produced protease, 10 produced pectinase, 7 produced cellulose and 5 produced xylanase with different zones of inhibition. *Lactobacillus plantarium* produced all the enzymes tested for. For the fifty *S. cerevisiae* isolated, 10 isolates exhibited amylase production, 5 produced cellulase, 8 produced protease, 7 produced pectinase and 2 produced xylanase with different zones of inhibitions. *S. cerevisiae* 25 produced all the enzymes tested (amylase, protease, cellulose, pectinase and xylanase). This research shows that fresh and soured palm wines are sources of LAB and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* which possess enzymes of industrial importance.

Keywords: Enzymatic potentials, Lactic Acid Bacteria, Palm Wine, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

INTRODUCTION

Palm wine is an alcoholic beverage resulting from the spontaneous fermentation of the sap of the palm, tree by indigenous microbes which consists of yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) and bacteria (mainly lactic Acid bacteria LAB and Acetic Acid bacteria AAB) (Onwuka, 2011; Okpara *et al.*, 2013). It is the fermented sap of certain varieties of the tropical plant of the palmae family which includes (*Elaeis guineensis*, *Raphia vinifera* and *Borassusf laellitter*). Fresh palm wine is a sweet, clear, colourless juice containing about 10-20% sugar, small amount of protein and minerals (Opara *et al.*, 2013). According to Onyka *et al.* (2009), it contains nutritionally important components including amino acids, proteins, vitamins and sugars and this makes palm wine a veritable medium for the growth of a consortium of microorganisms whose growth in turn changes the physiological conditions of the wine giving rise to competition and successions of organisms.

In traditional African societies, palm wine plays a significant role in the customary practices (AmoaAwua *et al.*, 2006). Over ten million people consume palm wine in West Africa (Onwuka 2011). Traditionally, it is believed that when taken by nursing mothers palm wine stimulates lactations and also has diuretic effects. Palm wine has also been used to enhance potency due to yeast cell concentration. (Amoa- Awu *et al.*, 2006).

Despite all the good qualities of palm wine, it is highly perishable due to fermentation which starts soon after the sap is collected through a process called tapping and within an hour or two, it becomes reasonably high in alcohol (up to 4%). If palm wine is allowed to continue to ferment for more than 24hrs, it starts to turn into vinegar. This makes it

unacceptable to consumers. (Awu *et al.*, 2006). Fermentation in palm wine is possible because it constitutes a good growth medium for numerous microorganisms especially for yeast, lactic acid and Acetic acid bacteria (Bechemet *et al.*, 2007). *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* constitutes about 70% of the total yeast of palm wine and enzymatic activities of these microbes are believed to be responsible for the conversion of sugar in palm sap to alcohol and after a short time while bacteria induce the conversion of alcohol into vinegar (Onwuka, 2011).

According to Abolhasan *et al.* (2007), it is due to the enzymatic activities of microbes such as *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, lactic acid bacteria and Acetic acid bacteria that lead to the souring of the palm wine after 24 hours of tapping. They do these by oxidizing the ethanol content of the palm wine to acetic acid by catalytic reactions of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase which are located on the periplasmic side of their cytoplasmic membrane. These enzymes are important in the industrial production of Acetic acid (Ameh *et al.*, 2011).

The aim of this research conducted in 2019 was to determine the enzymatic potentials of lactic acid bacteria and *saccharomyces cerevisiae* isolated from fresh and soured palm wine.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.0 Sample collection

Fifty (50) samples of fresh wine obtained from different oil palm trees (*Elaeagnis guineensis*) were aseptically collected using sterile 25 ml Screw-capped bottles from palm wine tapers in Ariam, Umudike and Umunneochi in Abia State. The samples were quickly taken to the laboratory of Microbiology Department, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike within two hours of collection for analyses. The samples were divided into two halved and one half was kept for 48 hrs to 72 hrs to obtain soured palm wine samples.

2.1 Isolation of Lactic Acid Bacteria

For this purpose, 10 ml each of the fresh and soured palm wine samples was serially diluted in sterile peptone water and 0.1 ml aliquots of appropriate dilution was spread plated in triplicates on sterile De Man Rogosa sharpe agar (MRS) agar plates and incubated anaerobically for 48 hours at 37°C. The typical LAB isolates were sub-cultured by streaking on fresh MRS agar plates to obtain pure cultures which were stored in the refrigerator at 4°C till further use (Cheesbrough, 2012).

2.2 Characterization and Identification of bacterial isolates

The pure LAB isolates were subjected to cultural and microscopic examinations as well as biochemical and sugar fermentation tests (Cheesbrough, 2012).

2.3 Isolation of yeasts from fresh and soured palm wine samples

Both the fresh and soured palm wine samples were shaken vigorously by hand and 1 ml of the sample was taken using sterile pipette and serially diluted in peptone water in test tubes. Then 0.1 ml aliquot of suitable dilution was spread plated in triplicate on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plates containing 0.05 mg/ml of chloramphenicol and gentamicin to inhibit bacterial growth. The inoculated plates were incubated at 25 °C for 48 hrs. The morphological characteristics and pigmentation on media of the colonies that developed were recorded while the colonies were purified by streaking on PDA plates and isolates were stored on slopes of PDA and kept in the refrigerator at 4°C till further use (Barnett *et al.*, 2002). Microscopy examination of the yeast was carried out according to Adenaike (2006) by emulsifying a loopful of an isolate under test on a clean slide with a drop of distilled water. The film was spread to make a thin film and then air dried after which it was stained with a methylene blue dye and observed with a light microscope under x10 and x40 objective lenses.

2.4 Qualitative screening of isolates for production of extracellular enzymes using Plate Assay Method Purification of isolate

The isolated pure strains were cultured into 50ml of Nutrient broth (for LAB) and Potato Dextrose broth for yeast) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37°C. After incubation, the broth was centrifuged at 5000rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatant containing the extracellular enzyme was used for the enzyme assay.

2.4.1 Production of Xylanase enzyme

The production of xylanase enzyme was carried out using screening medium containing Birch Wood Xylan as a substrate (Mahjabeensaleem *et al.*, 2002). The plate assay was performed using agar plate amended with Birch wood Xylan. The Agar plates were prepared by mixing 1% of Birchwood Xylan with 1.7% Agar. After solidification of the agar, wells were cut aseptically using sterile cork borer puncher for 10mm diameter and the culture filtrate was poured to the wells. The plates were incubated for 24 hr at 37°C. The observation of zone around the wells, 0.1% of Congo red solution was over layered on the medium and kept for 15 minutes. 1M NaCl was applied to make the zone visible and

clear (Ali Osman et al., 2010). The better zone forming species which was capable of liberating 1Mm equivalent of Xylose in one minute (Rifaat et al., 2005) was used for further study.

2.4.2 Production of Amylase enzyme

Qualitative determination of amylase production was carried out using Well Assay Method with some modifications. The agar plates were prepared and fortified with 1% of starch and 1.5% of agar for well-cut assay. After agar solidification, 10 mm diameter of well was cut out aseptically using Cork Borer. The well was filled with the culture filtrate (100 μ L), incubated for 24 hrs at 37°C. The agar was overlaid with 1% of iodine solution and hydrolytic zone around the well (clear zone) was measured. The negative control was set up by adding sterile water in a separate well.

2.4.3 Production of Cellulase enzyme

This was carried out by plate assay method using screening medium containing 1% (w/v) carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC). After solidification of Agar, the wells were cut aseptically by cork borer puncher for 10mm diameter and the culture filtrate was poured to the well then the plates and incubated for 24 hr at 37°C. To visualize the hydrolysis zone, the plates were flooded with 0.1% Congo red solution and washed with 1 M NaCl. The formation of a clear zone of hydrolysis indicated cellulose degradation. The ratio of the clear zone diameter to colony diameter was measured in order to select for the highest cellulase producer. The largest ratio was assumed to contain the highest activity (Salleh, 2000).

2.4.4 Screening of Isolates for Pectinase Activity

This was carried out using pectinase screening agar medium (PSAM). The medium composition is (g/l): Peptone 0.5, Beef extracts 0.3, NaCl 0.5, Agar 15, and Pectin 4.0. These were dissolved in distilled water (pH 7.0). The medium was sterilized and poured in a petri dish and allowed to gel. After, wells were cut aseptically by cork borer punch of 10mm diameter and the culture filtrate was poured then the plate was incubated at 30°C for 24 hours to 2 weeks. At the end of the incubation period, the plates were flooded with 50 mM Potassium iodide-iodine solution. A clear halo zone around the colonies indicates the ability of an isolate to produce pectinase (Beg *et al.*, 2000).

2.4.5 Screening of Isolates for Protease Activity

Proteolytic activity was detected by caesin hydrolysis on agar plate containing Yeast Nitrogen Base (YNB, DIFECO) medium supplemented with 0.5% of casino, 0.5% of glucose and 2% of agar (w/v) pH 7.0 (Larsen *et al.*, 1998). The medium was sterilized and poured in a petri dish and allowed to gel. Thereafter, wells of 10 mm were cut aseptically by cork borer punch and the culture filtrate was inoculated in the well. Then the plates were incubated at 28°C for 24 hours to 8 days. Enzyme activity was indicated by the formation of clear zone around the colonies after precipitation with 1m HCl solution (Rifaat *et al.*, 2005).

3.0 RESULT

Table 1 shows the different LAB isolated from different palm wine samples with their morphological, microscopically and biochemical characteristics. They include *Lactobacillus plantarium* and *Leuconostoc mesenteriodes*.

Result shows that 88 LAB isolated were from both the fresh and soured palm wine samples. *L. plantarium* and *L. mesenteriodes* had a percentage occurrence of 54.5 and 45.5 respectively (Table 2).

Saccharomyces cerevisiae and *Saccharomyces uvarum* were the yeasts isolated from the fresh and soured palm wine samples (Table 3).

From Table 4, 82 yeast isolates were recovered from the palm wine samples. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Saccharomyces uvarum* had percentage occurrence of 60.97 and 39.03 respectively.

The result of Total Viable Plate Counts (TVPL) for bacteria from both fresh and soured palm wines is presented in Table 5. For the fresh sample, the highest TVPL was 5.0×10^7 CFU/ml while the lowest value was 4.5×10^5 CFU/mL. The Total Lactic Acid Bacteria Plate Count (TLABPC) for the fresh sample was 4.4×10^7 CFU/mL while the least values was 3.7×10^5 CFU/mL. For the soured samples, the highest TVPL was 6.1×10^7 CFU/mL while the lowest was 6.0×10^5 CFU/mL. The highest TLABPC for the soured sample was 3.0×10^7 CFU/mL while the lowest value was 3.0×10^5 CFU/mL.

The result Enzyme production by various LAB isolated from both fresh and soured palm wine samples shows that LAB30 which is *Lactobacillus plantarium* showed activity for the five enzymes namely amylase, cellulase, protease, pectinase and xylanase (Table 6).

Table 7 shows that isolate *Saccharomyces 25* which is *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was the only yeast isolate that gave activity for the five enzymes tested.

Table 1: Morphological and biochemical characteristics of LAB isolated from fresh and soured palm wine samples

Colonial Feature	Gram Reaction	Cell Arrangement	Catalase	Oxidase	Coagulase	Indole	Citrate	Motility	Methyl Red	Voges-Proskauer	Glucose	Lactose	Manitol	Sucrose	Probable Isolate
Milky white and lenticular	Gram +	Cocci and chained	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	AG	AG	AG	A	Leuconostoc mesenteroides
White and small	Gram +	Long rod	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	A	A	AG	A	L. actobacillus plantarium

Key + = Positive - = Negative, AG = Acid and gas production, A = Acid production, G = Gas production.

Table 2: Percentage occurrence of LAB isolated from fresh and soured palm wine samples

Isolates	No of isolates	Percentage occurrence
Lactobacillus plantarium	48	54.5%
Leuconostoc mesenteroides	40	45.5%
Total	88	100%

Table 3: Isolation and identification of yeasts from fresh and soured palm wine samples

Probable isolate	Morphological Characteristics	Microscopic Characteristics	Sugar utilization				
			Glucose	Sucrose	Lactose	Mannitol	
Saccharomyces cerevisiae	Small White to creamy colonies with thick surface	convex oval shaped cells	Actively budding yeast with	A	NAG	NAG	A
Saccharomyces uvarum	Large creamy and unobtrusively raised colonies with small round edges	raised oval shape	Budding yeast cell with	G	AG	AG	A

Key: A= Acid production, G = Gas production, AG = Acid and Gas production, NAG = No Acid and Gas production.

Table 4: Percentage occurrence of yeast isolated from fresh and soured palm wine samples

Isolates	Number of isolates	Percentage occurrence
Saccharomyces cerevisiae	50	60.97%
Saccharomyces uvarum	32	39.03%
Total	82	100%

Table 5: Total Viable Plate Count of bacterial isolated from fresh and soured palm wine samples (CFU/mL)

Sample code	Sample type	TYPC	TLABPC	Sample code	Sample type	TYPC	TLABPC
FPW1	Fresh	6.7×10^6	6.1×10^6	SPW1	Soured	7.0×10^6	5.5×10^6
FPW2	Fresh	5.5×10^6	4.8×10^6	SPW2	Soured	6.1×10^6	3.6×10^6
FPW3	Fresh	4.6×10^6	4.1×10^6	SPW3	Soured	5.0×10^6	3.9×10^6
FPW4	Fresh	5.9×10^6	5.3×10^6	SPW4	Soured	6.1×10^6	4.0×10^6
FPW5	Fresh	6.9×10^6	6.0×10^6	SPW5	Soured	7.9×10^6	3.1×10^6
FPW6	Fresh	5.1×10^6	4.5×10^6	SPW6	Soured	6.0×10^6	2.9×10^6
FPW7	Fresh	4.9×10^6	4.2×10^6	SPW7	Soured	5.1×10^6	3.0×10^6
FPW8	Fresh	6.3×10^5	5.1×10^5	SPW8	Soured	7.2×10^5	4.8×10^5

FPW9	Fresh	6.9×10^5	6.2×10^5	SPW9	Soured	7.1×10^5	6.4×10^5
FPW10	Fresh	7.0×10^5	6.3×10^5	SPW10	Soured	7.2×10^5	6.6×10^5
FPW11	Fresh	5.9×10^5	4.7×10^5	SPW11	Soured	6.6×10^5	3.4×10^5
FPW12	Fresh	6.8×10^5	5.9×10^5	SPW12	Soured	8.7×10^5	4.9×10^5
FPW13	Fresh	3.2×10^7	2.5×10^7	SPW13	Soured	4.1×10^7	2.5×10^7
FPW14	Fresh	4.1×10^7	3.4×10^7	SPW14	Soured	5.1×10^7	2.8×10^7
FPW15	Fresh	2.7×10^7	2.0×10^7	SPW15	Soured	3.9×10^7	1.4×10^7
FPW16	Fresh	5.0×10^7	4.4×10^7	SPW16	Soured	6.1×10^7	3.0×10^7
FPW17	Fresh	2.2×10^7	1.6×10^7	SPW17	Soured	3.7×10^7	1.3×10^7
FPW18	Fresh	3.8×10^7	2.6×10^7	SPW18	Soured	5.2×10^7	1.7×10^7
FPW19	Fresh	5.9×10^6	4.1×10^6	SPW19	Soured	6.2×10^6	3.2×10^6
FPW20	Fresh	2.1×10^7	1.8×10^7	SPW20	Soured	3.0×10^7	1.1×10^7
FPW21	Fresh	4.5×10^5	3.7×10^5	Spw21	Soured	6.0×10^5	3.0×10^5
FPW22	Fresh	3.7×10^6	2.8×10^6	Spw22	Soured	4.5×10^6	1.9×10^6
FPW23	Fresh	5.2×10^5	4.5×10^5	Spw23	Soured	6.4×10^5	3.5×10^5
FPW24	Fresh	6.0×10^5	5.6×10^5	Spw24	Soured	7.1×10^5	4.0×10^5
FPW25	Fresh	4.0×10^6	3.6×10^6	Spw25	Soured	5.3×10^6	2.9×10^6

Key: FPW = Fresh palm wine. SPW = Soured palm wine. TYPC = Total Yeast Plate Count. TLABPC = Total Lactic Acid Bacteria Plate Count.

Table 6: Enzyme production by LAB from fresh and soured palm wine samples (mm)

Enzyme producing LAB isolates	Amylase	Cellulase	Protease	Pectinase	Xylanase
LAB2	5.0	0.0	3.0	4.0	0.0
LAB5	5.0	0.0	4.0	0.0	0.0
LAB10	6.0	5.0	0.0	2.8	0.0
LAB15	4.5	4.2	0.0	3.0	0.0
LAB17	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	3.0
LAB25	4.0	0.0	5.2	3.2	0.0
LAB27	5.2	0.0	6.0	0.0	0.0
LAB30	8.2	7.0	8.0	7.0	5.0
LAB32	0.0	0.0	3.0	6.0	6.0
LAB35	6.0	0.0	2.8	0.0	0.0
LAB40	6.2	0.0	4.0	0.0	0.0
LAB41	7.0	2.8	0.0	0.0	2.0
LAB45	5.0	2.0	0.0	6.3	0.0
LAB49	4.0	0.0	3.5	5.0	0.0
LAB52	3.2	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
LAB58	5.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	0.0
LAB70	5.0	0.0	4.2	0.0	0.0
LAB71	6.0	3.0	0.0	4.8	0.0
LAB73	6.2	0.0	0.0	3.0	0.0
LAB77	3.8	0.0	4.0	0.0	0.0
LAB83	4.8	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
LAB87	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	3.0

Table 7: Enzyme production by Yeast isolates from fresh and soured palm wine samples (mm)

Yeast isolate	Amylase	Cellulase	Protease	Pectinase	Xylanase
Saccharomyces1	0.0	0.0	2.8	2.0	0.0
Saccharomyces 5	3.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0
Saccharomyces 10	3.0	3.0	4.0	0.0	0.0
Saccharomyces 11	2.8	0.0	3.0	2.2	0.0
Saccharomyces 17	4.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	0.0
Saccharomyces 25	5.0	3.8	4.0	4.4	3.0
Saccharomyces 30	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Saccharomyces 31	0.0	0.0	2.0	3.2	0.0
Saccharomyces 33	2.0	2.0	0.0	3.0	0.0

Saccharomyces 34	3.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0
Saccharomyces 42	3.2	2.0	0.0	0.0	2.0
Saccharomyces 48	2.8	0.0	3.0	0.0	0.0
Saccharomyces 49	3.4	0.0	2.8	0.0	0.0

4.0 DISCUSSION

This work shows the enzymatic potentials of lactic acid bacteria and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* from fresh and soured palm wine. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* has been confirmed to be the dominant yeast species present in the different Palm wine samples analysed and it contributes to the fermentation of the palm sap to palm wine by utilizing the sugar contents of the palm sap. Similar yeast was isolated by Obi *et al* (2015) in the assessment of microbial growth in fresh Raphia palm wine. *Lactobacillus plantarium* and *Leuconostoc mesenteriodes* contributed to the increment in the acidic content of the palm wine thereby giving it a soured test after 24hours of tapping. Similar result was reported by Ouoba *et al*. (2012). These LAB also control the growth of undesirable microorganisms such as Enterobacteriaceae by their acid and hydrogen peroxide production (Santiago-urbina *et al.*, 2013). The method of tapping, collection, and location of the palm tree may contribute to microbial species present in the palm wine samples.

Palm sap is a nutrient rich medium capable of supporting the growth of non-pathogenic microbes which includes lactic acid bacteria and yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*). Considering the population of various microorganism in palm wine, there are different factors that are important in this regard such as insects and larvae infestation which contributes to the contamination of the product. Oozing of the sap can be facilitated by cutting a thin slice of the walls of the receptacle daily to expose a fresh layer daily by palm wine tapper and this physically remove the microbes that have colonized the walls of the receptacle thereby reducing the microbial loads in the chamber. The season also affects the microbial population in the palm wine samples as it was reviewed that palm wine harbors higher microbial population in dry season than in wet season. (Stringinin *et al.*, 2014). Little variation occurred in the population of yeast and LAB in the fresh and soured palm samples analyzed. Therefore, palm wine is a good and cheap source of these enzymes.

CONCLUSION

Lactobacillus planetarium and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* were found to possess amylase, cellulase, protease, pectinase and xylanase activity. This shows that fresh and soured palm wines are good sources of industrial enzymes.

REFERENCES

1. Abolhassan M.F., Sepehr, S. I. M., Shabani, A., Soudi, M.R. and Moosavi-Nejad, S.Z. (2007), Purification and characterization of Membrane-Bound Quinoprotein Alcohol Dehydrogenase from a Native Strain of Acetobacter, Journal of Biological Sciences, 7(2): 315-320
2. Adenaike O, Ameh JB, Whong CMZ (2006) Comparative studies of the fermentative capacity of baker's yeast and local yeast strains (*Saccharomyces* species) isolated from fermented beverages. Annual Conference of Nigerian Society of Microbiology.
3. Alcantara – Hennadez R.J., Podriguez- Alvarez, J.A Valenzuela – Encinas F.A Gutierrez – Miceli F.A, and Dendoven, L. (2010), The bacteria community in “taberna” a traditional beverage of southern Moaco Letters in Applied Microbiology 51 (5): 558 – 563.
4. Ameh, S.J; Obodozie, O.O., Olorunfemi, O.P., Okoliko, E.I. and Ochekepe, N.A. (2011). Potetntial of gladiolus corms as antimicrobial agent in food processing and traditional medicine. Journal of Microbiology and Antimicrobials, 3(1): 8-12.
5. Amendola J, Rees N (2002). Understanding Baking: The Art and Science of Baking . John Wiley and Sons. p. 36. ISBN 978-0-471-40546-7
6. Amoa-Awua, W.K., Sampson, E. and Tano-Debrah, K. (2006). Growth of yeasts, lactic and acetic acid bacteria in palm wine during tapping and fermentation from felled oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*) in Ghana, Journal of Applied Microbiology, 101: 599-606.
7. Amoozegar, M. A., Malekzadeh, F., and Malik, K. A. (2003). ”Production of amylase by newly isolated moderate halophile, *Halobacillus* sp. strain MA-2”. Journal of microbiological methods, 52 (3), 353-359.
8. Ashraf, H., Iqbal, J., and Qadeer, M. A. (2003). “Production of alpha amylase by *Bacillus licheniformis* using an economical medium”. Bioresource Technology, 87 (1), 57-61.
9. Ashraf, H., MA, Q., and Iqbal, J. (2005). “Pearl millet, a source of alpha amylase production by *Bacillus licheniformis*”. Bioresource technology , 96 (10), 1201-1204.
10. B. Prakash, M. Vidyasagar, M.S. Madhukumar, G. Muralikrishna, K. Sreeramulu, (2009). “Production, purification, and characterization of two extremely halotolerant, thermostable, and alkali-stable a-amylases from *Chromohalobacter* sp. TVSP 101”, Process Biochemistry, 44 , 210-215.,

11. Babu, K. R., and Satyanarayana, T. (1995). "α-Amylase production by thermophilic *Bacillus coagulans* in solid state fermentation". *Process Biochemistry*, 30 (4), 305-309.
12. Balkan, B., and Ertan, F. , (2007). "Production of a-amylase from *Penicillium chrysogenum* under solid-state fermentation by using some agricultural by-products". *Food Technology Biotechnology* , 45 , 439-442
13. Bankar AV, Kumar AR, Zinjarde SS (2009). "Environmental and industrial applications of *Yarrowia lipolytica*". *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* . 84 (5): 847–865.
14. Barneth J, Payne R, Yarrow D (2002) *Yeast: Characteristics and Identification*. 2nd Edition Cambridge Univ Press.
15. Bassir, O. (1999). Observation on the fermentation of palm wine. *West African Journal of Biology and Applied chemistry* 6: 20-25. .
16. Bechem, E.E T., Omoloko, C., Nwaga, D. and Titanji, V.P.K. (2007). Characterization of palm wine yeasts using osmotic, ethanol tolerance and the isozyme polymorphism of alcohol dehydrogenase, *Archiv fur Mikrobiologie*, 83: 237-245
17. Bhargav, S., Panda, B. P., Ali, M., and Javed, S. (2008). "Solid-state fermentation: an overview". *Chemical and Biochemical Engineering Quarterly* , 22 (1), 49-70.
18. Bin, G., X. Laisu, D. Youfang and L. Yanquan, (1999). "Screening of alpha amylase high-producing strains from *Bacillus subtilis*", *Journal of Zhejiang* , 23, 88-92.
19. Botstein D, Fink GR (2011). "Yeast: an experimental organism for 21st Century biology". *Genetics*. 189 (3): 695–704.
20. Cappitelli F, Sorlini C (2008). "Microorganisms attack synthetic polymers in items representing our cultural heritage" . *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*. 74 (3): 564–569.
21. Carlsen, M. Nielsen, J. Villadsen, J., (1996). "Growth and a-amylase production by *Aspergillus oryzae* during continuous cultivations", *Journal of Biotechnology*., 45 , 81-93.
22. Chandrasekhar, K., Sreevani, S., Seshapani, .P. (2012). A review on palm wine. *International Journal of Research Biology of Science*, 2 (1): 33 – 38.
23. Cheesbrough, M. (2012). *Biochemical Tests to identify bacteria. Laboratory practice in tropical countries* cheesbrough M (ed). Combridge (ed)pp 63 – 70
24. Coronado, M. J., Vargas, C., Hofemeister, J., Ventosa, A., and Nieto, J. J. (2000). "Production and biochemical characterization of an α-amylase from the moderate halophile *Halomonas meridiana*". *FEMS microbiology letters* , 183 (1), 67-71,.
25. Couto, S. R., and Sanromán, M. A. (2006). "Application of solid-state fermentation to food industry-a review" *Journal of Food Engineering*, 76 (3), 291-302.
26. Das, S., Singh, S., Sharma, V., & Soni, M. L. (2011). "biotechnological applications of industrially important amylase enzyme". *International Journal of Pharmacology & Biochemistry Sciences* , 2 (1),.
27. De Almeida Siqueira, E. M., Mizuta, K., and Giglio, J. R. (1997). "Pycnoporus sanguineus : a novel source of α-amylase". *Mycological research*, 101 (2), 188-190.
28. Djekrif-Dakhmouche, S. Gheribi-Aoulmi, Z. Meraihi, Z. Bennamoun, L. (2005). "Application of a statistical design to the optimization of culture medium for α-amylase production by *Aspergillus niger* ATCC 16404 grown on orange waste powder", *Journal of Food Engineering*. 73, 190-197,
29. Drauz, K., Gröger, H., and May, O. (2010). (Edition) *Enzyme catalysis in organic synthesis: a comprehensive Handbook*, John Wiley & Sons, (2012), Souza, P. M. D., "Application of microbial α-amylase in industry-A review", *Brazilian Journal of microbiology* , 41 (4), 850-861, May
30. Duyff RL (2012). *American Dietetic Association Complete Food and Nutrition Guide, Revised and Updated (4th ed.)*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt. pp. 256–257.
31. Erdal, S. E. R. K. A. N., and Taskin, M. E. S. U. T. (2010). "Production of alpha-amylase by *Penicillium expansum* MT-1 in solid-state fermentation using waste Loquat (*Eriobotrya japonica* Lindley) kernels as substrate". *Romanian Biotechnological Letters*, 15 (3), 5342-5350,.
32. Ezeagu, I.E, Fafunso, M.A and Ejezie, F.E (2003) Biochemical constituents of palm wine. *Ecology of Food Nutrition* 42 (3): 213-222.
33. Ezeronye O.U and Okerentugba, P.O. (2001), Genetic and physiological variants of yeast selected from palm wine.
34. Faparasi S.I and Bassin O. (1972). Factors affecting the quality of palm wine, period of tapping a palm tree. *West African Journal of Biological and Applied Chemistry* 15: 17 – 23.
35. Faparusi, S.I. (1981). Sugar identified in *Raphra* palm wine. *Food Chemistry* 7 (2): 81-86
36. Feller, G., Le Bussy, O., and Gerday, C. (1998). Expression of psychrophilic genes in mesophilic hosts: assessment of the folding state of a recombinant α-amylase. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 64 (3), 1163-1165.
37. Gibson M (2010). *The Sommelier Prep Course: An Introduction to the Wines, Beers, and Spirits of the World* . John Wiley and Sons. p. 361.
38. Gomes, I., Gomes, J., and Steiner, W. (2003). "Highly thermostable amylase and pullulanase of the extreme thermophilic eubacterium *Rhodothermus marinus* : production and partial characterization". *Bioresource technology*, 90 (2), 207-214.

39. Goto, C.E.; Barbosa, E.P.; Kistner, L.C.; Moreira, F.G.; Lenartovicz, V. and Peralta, R.M. (1998). "Production of amylase by *Aspergillus fumigatus* utilizing alpha-methyl-D-glycoside, a synthetic analogue of maltose, as substrate". *FEMS Microbiol Lett* 167 , 139-143.
40. Gupta, R., Gigras, P., Mohapatra, H., Goswami, V. K., and Chauhan, B. (2003). "Microbial α -amylases: a biotechnological perspective", *Process Biochemistry*, 38 (11), 1599-1616,
41. Haki, G. D., and Rakshit, S. K. (2003). "Developments in industrially important thermostable enzymes: a review". *Bioresource Technology*, 89 (1), 17-34,
42. Haq, I., Ali, S., Javed, M. M., Hameed, U., Saleem, A., Adnan, F., and Qadeer, M. A. (2010). "roduction of alpha amylase from a randomly induced mutant strain of *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* and its application as a desizer in textile industry" *Pak J Bot*, 42 (1), 473-484.
43. Hayashida, S. Teramoto, Y. (1986). "Production and characteristics of raw-starch-digestinga-amylase from a protease negative *Aspergillus ficuum* mutant", *Applied and environmental microbiology.*, 52 , 1068-1073.
44. Karamoko, D., Djeni, N. T., N'guessan, K. F., Bouatenin, K. M. J. and Dje, K. M. 2012. The biochemical and microbiological quality of palm wine samples produced at different periods during tapping and changes which occurred during their storage. *Food Control* 26 (2): 504-511.
45. Kathiresan, K., and Manivannan, S. (2006). "-Amylase production by *Penicillium fellutanum* isolated from mangrove rhizosphere soil". *African journal of Biotechnology*, 5 (10).
46. Kenneth A. Laderman, Bradley R. Davis, Henry C. Krutzsch, Marc S. Lewis, Y. V. Griko, Peter L. Privalov, and Christia B. Anfinsen, (1993). "The Purification and Characterization of an Extremely Thermostable α -Amylase from the Hyperthermophilic Archaeobacterium *Pyrococcus furiosus*", *Journal of Biological Chemistry* , 268 (32), 24394-24401.
47. Knox, A. M., du Preez, J. C., and Kilian, S. G. (2004). "Starch fermentation characteristics of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strains transformed with amylase genes from *Lipomyces kononenkoae* and *Saccharomycopsis fibuligera* ". *Enzyme and Microbial Technology*, 34 (5), 453-460.
48. Konsoula, Z., Liakopoulou-Kyriakides M., (2007). "Co-production of alpha-amylase and beta-galactosidase by *Bacillus subtilis* in complex organic substrates." *Bioresource Technology*, 98, 150-157.
49. Kunamneni, A., Permaul, K., and Singh, S. (2005). "Amylase production in solid state fermentation by the thermophilic fungus *Thermomyces lanuginosus*". *Journal of bioscience and bioengineering* , 100(2), 168-171.
50. Kurtzman CP (2006). "Detection, identification and enumeration methods for spoilage yeasts". In Blackburn CDW. *Food spoilage microorganisms* . Cambridge, England: Woodhead Publishing . pp. 28–54. ISBN 978-1-85573-966-6.
51. Kurtzman CP, Fell JW (2005). in: *The Yeast Handbook*, Gábor P, de la Rosa CL, eds. Biodiversity and Ecophysiology of Yeasts. Berlin: Springer. pp. 11–30.
52. Lasekan O., Buctter, A and Christlbauer, M (2007), investigation of important odorant of palm, wine (*Elaeisqueensis*). *Food chemistry* 105 (1) 15 -23.
53. Legras J. L, Merdinoglu D, Cornuet J. M, Karst F (2007). "Bread, beer and wine: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* diversity reflects human history". *Molecular Ecology*. 16 (10): 2091–2102.
54. Lévêque, E., Janeček, Š., Haye, B., and Belarbi, A. (2000). "Thermophilic archaeal amylolytic enzymes". *Enzyme and Microbial Technology*, 26 (1), 3-14.
55. Madhavan A, Srivastava A, Kondo A, Bisaria VS (2012). "Bioconversion of lignocellulose-derived sugars to ethanol by engineered *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* ". *Critical Reviews in Biotechnology* . 32 (1): 22–48.
56. Moller, K. Sharif, M.Z. Olsson, L. (2004). "Production of fungal a-amylase by *Saccharomyces kluyveri* in glucose-limited cultivations", *Journal of Biotechnology* , 111, 311-318.
57. Murray, P.R., E.J. Baron, J.H. Jorgensen, M.L. Landry, and M.A. Pfaller. 2007. *Manual of Clinical Microbiology*. 9th ed. ASM Press, Washington D.C.
58. Naknean P., Meenune, M, and Roudant, G. (2010). Characteristics of palm sap harvested in songkraprovince southern Thailand. *International Food Research Journal* 17 (4): 977 -986.
59. Nur Ami, R., Abu Bakar, F and Dzulkifly, M.H. (2013). Determination of volatile compounds in fresh and fermented Nipa Sap (*Nypafructicans*) using slatic headspace gas chromatography – mass spectiometry (GC – MS) *International Food Research Journal* 20 (1): 369 – 376.
60. Nwachukwu, I.N, Ibekwe, V. INwabueze, R.N and Anyanwu B.N (2006). Characterization of palm wine yeast isolates for industrial utilization. *African Journal of Biotechnology* 5 (19): 1725 – 1728.
61. Obi, C.N., Ogbulie, J.N and Nkwo, A.M. (2015). Assessment of microbial growth and survival in fresh raffia palm wine from umuariaga community, Ikwuano L.G.A Abia State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Current Microbiological and Applied Science* 4 (1): 484 – 494. .
62. Obire, O. (2005), Activity of zymomonas species in palm sap obtained from three areas in Edo State Nigeria *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management* 9 (1): 25 – 30..
63. Oboh, G. (2005). "Isolation and characterization of amylase from fermented cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) wastewater". *African Journal of biotechnology* , 4 (10).
64. Okafor, N (1972). Palm wine yeasts from parts of Nigeria. *Journal of Food Science and Agriculture*, 23: 1399-1407

65. Okafor, N. (1978). Microbiology and biochemistry of Oil palm wine. *Advances in Applied Microbiology* 24: 237 – 256.
66. Onwuka, U. N. (2011). Performance evaluation of ohmic heating under a static medium on the pasteurization and quality parameters of palm wine (Raphia Hokeri). *Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering and Applied Science*, 2(1): 160-165
67. Opara, C.C., Ajoku, G. and Madumelu, N.O. (2013). Palm wine mixed culture fermentation kinetics, *Greener Journal of Physical Sciences*, 3(1): 028-037.
68. Ouoba, I., Kando, C., Parkouda, C., Sawadogo – Lingani H., Diawa, B and Sutherland, J.P. (2012). The microbiology of Bandji, Palm wine of Borassusakeassi from Burkina faso; identification and genotypic diversity of yeast, lactic acid and Acetic acid bacteria, *Journal of Applied Microbiology* 113 (6): 14 28 – 144..
69. Oyeku, O.M., Adeyemo, F.S., Kupoluyi, F.C., Abdulhadi, T.M. Davies, O.S., Yussuf, I.G., Sadiq, A.O. and Olatunji, O.O. (2009) techno-economic packaging of palm wine preservation and bottling technology for entrepreneur, *Global Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(1): 21-26.
70. Pandey, A., Nigam, P, Soccol, V., Singh, D., and Mohan, R. (2000). "Advances in microbial amylases". *Biotechnology and Applied Biochemistry*, 31 , 135-152,.
71. Pandey, A., Selvakumar, P., Soccol, C. R., and Nigam, P. (1999). "Solid state fermentation for the production of industrial enzymes" *Current science* , 77 (1), 149-162.
72. Paquet., Croux, Goma and Soucaille, (1991). "Purification and characterization of the extracellular alpha-amylase from *Clostridium acetobutylicum* ATCC 824". *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* , 57 (1), 212-218.
73. Prakasham, R. S., Subba Rao, C., Sreenivas Rao, R., and Sarma, P. N. (2007). "Enhancement of acid amylase production by an isolated *Aspergillus awamori*". *Journal of applied microbiology* , 102 (1), 204-211,
74. Prasad Nooralabettu Krishna, (2011), "Enzyme Technology: Pacemaker of Biotechnology", PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd.
75. Price C (Full 2015). "The healing power of compressed yeast" MID 24278784 .
76. Priest FG, Stewart GG (2006). *Handbook of Brewing* . CRC Press. p. 84.
77. Ramachandran, S., Patel, A. K., Nampoothiri, K. M., Chandran, S., Szakacs, G., Soccol, C. R., and Pandey, A. (2004). "Alpha amylase from a fungal culture grown on oil cakes and its properties". *Brazilian Archives of Biology and Technology*, 47 (2), 309-317.
78. Ramesh, M. V., and Lonsane, B. K. (1990). "Critical importance of moisture content of the medium in alpha-amylase production by *Bacillus licheniformis* M27 in a solid-state fermentation system". *Applied microbiology and biotechnology*, 33 (5), 501-505.
79. Saito and Yamamoto,. (1975). "Regulatory factors affecting alpha-amylase production in *Bacillus licheniformis*". *Journal of bacteriology* , 121 (3), 848-856.
80. Santiago – Urbina, J.A., Verdugo – Valdez, A.G. and Ruiz Terna, F. (2013), Physicochemical and microbiological changes during tapping of palm sap to produce an alcoholic beverage caved "Taberna" which is produced in the south east of maxico food control 33 (1): 58 62.
81. Sindhu, R., Suprabha, G. N., and Shashidhar, S. (2009). "Optimization of process parameters for the production of a-amylase from *Penicillium janthinellum* (NCIM 4960) under solid state fermentation". *African Journal of Microbiology Research*, 3 (9), 498-503.
82. Singh H (2006). *Mycoremediation: Fungal Bioremediation* . p. 507. ISBN 978-0-470-05058-3
83. Sivaramakrishnan, S., Gangadharan, D., Nampoothiri, K. M., Soccol, C. R., and Pandey, (2006). A. "α-Amylases from Microbial Sources--An Overview on Recent Developments". *Food Technology & Biotechnology*, 44 (2).
84. Sivaramakrishnan, S., Gangadharan, D., Nampoothiri, K. M., Soccol, C. R., and Pandey, A. (2007). "Alpha amylase production by *Aspergillus oryzae* employing solid-state fermentation". *Journal of scientific and industrial research*, 66 (8), 621.
85. Smith A, Kraig B (2013). *The Oxford Encyclopedia of Food and Drink in America* . Oxford University Press. p. 440.
86. Soares EV, Soares HMVM (2012). "Bioremediation of industrial effluents containing heavy metals using brewing cells of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* as a green technology: A review". *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* . 19 (4): 1066–1083.
87. Sodhi, H.K.; Sharma, K.; Gupta, J.K. and Soni, S.K. (2005). "Production of a thermostable α-amylase from *Bacillus* sp. PS-7 by solid state fermentation and its synergistic use in the hydrolysis of malt starch for alcohol production". *Process Biochemistry*, 40 , 525-534.
88. Stringini, M., Comitini, F., Taccari, M. and Clani, M. (2009). Yeast diversity during tapping and fermentation of palm wine from Cameroon. *Food microbiology* 26 (4) 415 -420.
89. Sudo, S., Ishikawa, T., Sato, K., and Oba, T. (1994). "Comparison of acid-stable α-amylase production by *Aspergillus kawachii* in solid-state and submerged cultures". *Journal of fermentation and bioengineering* , 77 (5), 483-489.
90. Swamy, M.V. Seenayya, G. (1996). "Thermostable pullulanase and a-amylase activity from *Clostridium thermosulfurogenes* SV9 optimization of culture conditions for enzyme production" *Process Biochemistry*, 31 , 157-162.

91. Syu, M. J., and Chen, Y. H. (1997). "A study on the α -amylase fermentation performed by *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*". *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 65 (3), 237-247.
92. Tanyildizi, M.S. Ozer, D. Elibol, M. (2005). "Optimization of α -amylase production by *Bacillus* sp. using response surface methodology", *Process Biochemistry*, 40, 2291-2296.
93. Thaler M, Safferstein D (2014). *A Curious Harvest: The Practical Art of Cooking Everything* . Quarry Books. p. 129. ISBN 978-1-59253-928-4 .
94. Thippeswamy, S., Girigowda, K., and Mulimani, V. H. (2006). "Isolation and identification of alpha-amylase producing *Bacillus* sp. from dhal industry waste". *Indian Journal of Biochemistry and Biophysics* , 43 (5), 295.
95. Upgade, A., Nandeshwar,A., and Samant,L., (2011). "Assessment of fungal protease enzyme from French bean using *A. niger* by Solid State Fermentation", *Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology Research* , 1 , 45-51.
96. UzochukwuS.V.A., Balogh, E., Tucknoh, O., Lewis M. J. and Ngoddy, P.O. (1999). Role of palm wine yeast and bacteria in palm wine aroma. *Journal of food science and technology* 36 (4) : 301 – 304.
97. Vieille, K. Zeikus, G.J. (2001). "Hyperthermophilic enzymes: Sources, uses, and molecular mechanisms of thermostability", *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Review*, 65, 1-43.
98. Whong, S., Debra S, Delgado, S.I, and Klontz, K.C. (2006). Recalls of foods and Cosmetics Due to Microbial Contamination Reported to the U.S. Food and Drug Administration. *Journal of Food Protection*, Vol. 63, No. 8,Pp. 1113-1116
99. Y. Yoneda and B. Maruo, (1975). "Mutation of *Bacillus subtilis* Causing Hyperproduction of α -Amylase and Protease, and Its Synergistic Effect", *Journal of Bacteriology*, 124, 48-54,
100. Yang, S. S., and Wang, J. Y. (1999). "Protease and amylase production of *Streptomyces rimosus* in submerged and solid state cultivations". *Botanical Bulletin of Academia Sinica* , 40, 259-265.
101. *Yarrowia lipolytica* ". *Journal of Hazardous Materials* . 170 (1): 487–494.